

Original Article

Neonatal Morbidity and Mortality Pattern in a Tertiary Health Facility in the Niger Delta Region: A 2-Year Review

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ABSTRACT

Neonatal morbidity and mortality patterns could reflect the state of maternal and child health of a given area, and provide opportunities to strengthen health programs and interventions that do not achieve their set goals. The aim of the study was to review and document the neonatal morbidity and mortality pattern of the Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) in the last 2 years. A review of the medical records of neonates admitted into the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of the DELSUTH from 1st of January 2018 to 31st of December 2019 was undertaken with the view of documenting the morbidity and mortality pattern. Data extracted from admission records included socio-demographic data such as age, gender, place of birth, mode of delivery, maternal age, maternal educational status and occupation of fathers. Also documented were clinical diagnoses and treatment outcomes. The collected data were entered into a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet and analyzed. A total of 180 neonates were admitted over the period under review with 104 (57.8%) males and 76 (42.2%) females. The mean gestational age was 37 ± 4 weeks, and the mean admitting weight was 2.4 ± 1 Kg. Forty-five (25%) neonates had respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), 37 (20.6%) had neonatal sepsis, 36 (20%) had birth asphyxia and 32 (17.8%) had congenital anomalies. Fifty-four (30%) mortalities were recorded with the highest case fatality rate recorded among preterm neonates with RDS (37.8%). The leading causes of neonatal morbidities and mortalities at the study centre were RDS, neonatal sepsis, birth asphyxia and congenital anomalies.

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Specialty section:
This article was submitted to
Paediatrics, a section of JRBCS

Received: 09 July 2021
Accepted: 09 November, 2021
Published: 07 December, 2021

Citation:
Abolodje E, Ekpebe P, Onyeaso
U, Cummings H, Odion OH,
Ovili C,
Neonatal Morbidity and
Mortality Pattern in a Tertiary
Health Facility in the Niger
Delta Region: A 2-Year Review.
J Res
Bas Clin Sci 2(2):25-31.
DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.5768457

Access Code

<http://jrbc.org>

Keywords: Neonate, Morbidity, Mortality, Pattern, Niger Delta

INTRODUCTION

Global health indices show that developing countries, particularly those in sub-Saharan Africa, have the worst health indices with very high under-five morbidity and mortality.^{1,2} However, it is true that the data generated from these studies have shown that even within regions and countries, the findings are not homogenous.^{1,2} There is often a need to individually assess states or institutions

within regions or countries in order to identify more peculiar problems. Neonatal morbidity and mortality pattern in a given area could reflect the state of maternal and child health, and provide opportunities to strengthen health programs and make interventions where necessary.

Delta State University Teaching Hospital (DELSUTH) is a tertiary health facility that serves as a referral centre for primary and secondary health facilities in Delta state. The hospital has had a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) for the past 10 years of its existence. In 2010, McGill Ugwu³ conducted a prospective study over a 2-year period to determine the pattern of neonatal morbidity and mortality in DELSUTH. His findings revealed that neonatal sepsis, birth asphyxia and prematurity accounted for about 70% of admissions and mortalities, while neonatal tetanus had the highest case fatality rate (50%).³

Over the last decade, maternal and child health in Delta state and Nigeria at large has evolved with some innovations introduced into its programs. A notable example is the introduction of chlorhexidine cord care in Nigeria in the year 2012 in order to reduce the incidence of neonatal sepsis and mortality.⁴ It must also be stated that immunization coverage for both women and children have improved and this could have impacted positively on the health status of both women and children.^{5,6} However, it is not certain how these changes in the health sector have affected the morbidity and mortality pattern, especially those of maternal and child health. In the presence of these important changes that have occurred in the health sector, it becomes necessary to document the pattern of neonatal morbidities and mortalities in the neonatal unit of the DELSUTH and see how it differs from findings reported by McGill Ugwu about a decade ago.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in DELSUTH. Delta state is

one of the 36 states of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, and is located in the oil rich Niger Delta region. The DELSUTH is a tertiary hospital with a capacity to admit about 250 patients at a time. The NICU has a capacity to admit about 18 neonates with an in-born and an out-born section. As at the time of the study, the NICU had mechanical ventilators, radiant heaters, piped oxygen, and other equipments and devices for cardiopulmonary support of unstable neonates. The unit was headed by two neonatologists with support from resident doctors and nurses.

The study was a review of admitted cases in the NICU. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethics and Research committee of the hospital. The subjects included all neonates admitted into the NICU from 1st January 2018 to 31st December 2019. The subjects were identified from the admission register of the NICU by their hospital numbers after which their case files were retrieved from the Medical Records Unit. Data extracted from the case files included; hospital number, age, sex, gestational age, place of delivery, mode of delivery, maternal age, booking status, educational status of both parents, occupation of both parents, birth weight, clinical diagnoses and treatment outcomes. Data extracted were entered into Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet and was analyzed. Means were determined for continuous variables and frequencies were determined for categorical variables. Results were presented in tables and figures.

RESULTS

There were 206 admissions over the period under review, however, 26 (12.7%) neonates had incomplete data and were excluded from the study. The excluded cases were as follows; 6 cases of NNS, 5 cases of prematurity, 5 cases of asphyxia, 4 cases of congenital anomalies, 2 cases of suspected aspiration syndrome and 4 other cases.

One hundred and eighty cases were reviewed out of which 104 (56.8%) were males, 76 (42.3%) were

preterm neonates and 71 (39.4%) were neonates delivered via caesarean section as shown in table I. Also, most of the neonates were delivered in health facilities with only 12 (6.7%) neonates delivered at home as shown in figure 1.

Table I: Distribution of neonates into gender, maturity, place of delivery, mode of delivery, parity

Variable	Frequency (%)
Gender	
Male	104 (57.8)
Female	76 (42.2)
Maturity	
Preterm	070 (38.9)
Term	110 (61.1)
Place of Delivery	
Health facility	168 (93.3)
Home	012 (6.7)
Mode of Delivery	
SVD	109 (60.6)
C/Section	71 (39.4)
Parity	
Primi	058 (32.3)
Multipara	098 (54.4)
Grandmultipara	024 (13.3)

Figure 1: Place of Delivery

The age range of neonates was 1-672 hours, the mean weight was 2.42 (±0.95) kg, the mean gestational age was 37.19 (±3.95) weeks and the mean maternal age was 30.51 (±5.96) years as shown in table II. Eighty-nine (49.5%) neonates were admitted during

the first 24 hours of life, 67 (37.2%) neonates were admitted between 2nd and 7th day of life and 24(13.3%) neonates were admitted after the 1st week of life.

One hundred and two (56.7%) mothers had primary level of education, 60 (33.3%) mothers had secondary level of education and only 18 (10.0%) had tertiary level of education.

Table II: Range, minimum, maximum and mean of age, weight, gestational age and maternal age

Variable	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Age (hours)	671.00	1.00	672.00	87.20	125.63
GA (weeks)	16.00	25.00	41.00	37.19	3.95
Weight (Kg)	4.94	0.56	5.50	2.42	0.95
Maternal Age (years)	29.00	17.00	46.00	30.51	5.96

Twenty-four (14%) fathers were either unemployed or unskilled labourers (low social class), 116 (65%) were skilled workers or self employed (middle social class) and 38 (21%) fathers were professionals (high social class).

The commonest indications for admission were RDS, NNS and perinatal asphyxia as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Bar chart description of clinical diagnoses of neonates

RDS- Respiratory distress syndrome; NNJ- neonatal jaundice; NNS- neonatal sepsis, TTN- transient tachypnea of newborn

The commonest congenital anomalies were omphalocele, multiple congenital anomalies (VACTERYL) and spinal dysraphism as shown in table III

There were 71 (39.5%) discharges, 54 (30.0%) deaths, and 13 (7.2%) referred cases as shown in figure 3

More discharged cases were recorded among neonates with NNS, more deaths were recorded among neonates with RDS, and more DAMA were recorded among asphyxiated neonates as shown in figure 4.

Table III: Pattern of Congenital Anomalies

Congenital anomalies	Frequency (%)
Omphalocele	9 (27.3)
Multiple congenital anomaly (VACTERYL)	4 (12.1)
Spinal dysraphism	3 (9.1)
Gastroschisis	2 (6.1)
Hirschsprungs disease	2 (6.1)
Imperforate anus	2 (6.1)
Inguinal hernia	2 (6.1)
Duodenal atresia	2 (6.1)
Conjoin twins	1 (3.0)
Biliary atresia	1 (3.0)
Hemangioma	1 (3.0)
Unilateral ventriculomegaly	1 (3.0)
Esophageal atresia	1 (3.0)
Ambiguous genitalia	1 (3.0)
Encephalocele	1 (3.0)

Figure 3: Pie chart description of treatment outcomes: Deaths (Male=32; Female=22); DAMA- Discharge against medical advice (Male=20; Female=22) in a pie chart

Premature neonates with RDS had the highest case fatality rate, followed by NNS, congenital anomalies and asphyxia as shown in figure IV.

Figure 4: Distribution of treatment outcome for each diagnosis

DISCUSSION

The commonest indications for admissions were prematurity, perinatal asphyxia and neonatal sepsis accounting for more than two-third of the admissions. This finding is similar to report by McGill in the same facility about a decade ago. Prematurity, asphyxia and neonatal sepsis have been widely reported in the literature as the most important causes of neonatal morbidities both locally and globally.^{7,9} Though, McGill Ugwu reported neonatal sepsis as the leading cause for admission into the neonatal unit while the present study found prematurity with RDS as the leading cause of admission into the neonatal unit. Some authors have also reported a higher burden of premature neonates

requiring admission when compared to cases of neonatal sepsis or asphyxia.⁸⁻¹⁰ No case of neonatal tetanus was recorded over the period under review and this differs from the report by McGill Ugwu where there were 4 cases of neonatal tetanus with a 50% case fatality rate. It thus appears that the incidence of neonatal tetanus is on the decline in Nigeria even as reported by other authors.¹¹⁻¹³

Congenital anomalies in the present study accounted for 18.3% cases as against 2.5% of cases recorded by McGill Ugwu in his study. The prevalence of congenital anomalies from the present study is higher than values reported in the literature of less than 10%.^{10,14,15} Interestingly, most of these studies revealed that congenital anomalies now contribute significantly to both neonatal morbidity and mortality.^{9,13,15-18} The commonest congenital anomalies recorded in the present study were omphalocele, multiple congenital anomalies (VACTERYL) and spinal dysraphism. McGill Ugwu also reported spinal dysraphism and gastroschisis among the commonest congenital anomalies in his study.

The proportion of mortality recorded in the present series was 30%, a rate higher than 20.3% that was recorded about a decade ago in the present facility. The mortality proportion in the present study is higher than values recorded in Ibadan, southwestern Nigeria⁷, Jos, north-central Nigeria¹³ and Enugu, southeastern Nigeria.¹⁴ The mortality recorded is equally higher than what was reported in neonatal units of hospitals in India which recorded 18.69%⁸, Ethiopia which recorded 20%¹⁵ and Eastern Nepal which recorded 20.2%¹⁹. The reason for the high mortality in the present series is not clear, but it was very likely due to a combination of factors. It must be stated that over 50% of mothers in the present study had only primary level of education, and maternal level of education has been shown to have an inverse relationship with child survival.^{20,21} Also, the high burden of congenital anomalies from the present series could have contributed to the increased mortality seen at the centre as reported by other authors.¹⁶⁻¹⁹

Neonatal deaths recorded in this study were primarily due to RDS, birth asphyxia, congenital anomalies and neonatal sepsis. However, RDS, congenital anomalies and NNS contributed more to deaths, and had the highest case fatality rate of 37.8%, 34.4% and 32.4% respectively. Though prematurity, birth asphyxia and neonatal sepsis have been reported globally as the leading causes of neonatal mortality, some studies have shown that congenital anomalies is gradually becoming an important cause of neonatal mortality as stated earlier.^{9,13,15-18} The present study has shown that most deaths occurred within the first 24 hours of life and more than three-quarter deaths occurred within the first week of life. A similar finding has been reported in the literature.^{9,13,14}

Forty-one (23%) neonates were discharged against medical advice (DAMA) in the present series as against none that was reported by McGill Ugwu about a decade ago in this facility. It must be stated here that these neonates DAMA were lost to follow up and as a result their actual treatment outcome could not be ascertained. Discharge against medical advice has been reported in neonatal units in other institutions but the present study appears to be the highest recorded in the literature. The prevalence of DAMA in children in Nigeria hospitals is between 1.7-5.3%.²²⁻²⁴ The present study also revealed that more female neonates were DAMA despite the fact that they were more males admitted at the study centre, and this is consistent with a report from Sokoto.²² Some of the reasons why caregivers request for DAMA include lack of fund to sustain care, no improvement in clinical condition of neonate and prolonged hospital stay.^{22,23}

CONCLUSION

Prematurity, birth asphyxia and neonatal sepsis were the leading causes of admission of neonates in the present study. However, prematurity, birth asphyxia and congenital anomalies were the most common causes of mortality. The high mortality rate and the high DAMA

rate at the study centre are worrisome and require immediate attention.

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